

UTILITY PATTERN-ROOTED CLOUD SERVICE NEGOTIATION USING A MACHINE LEARNING-BASED, HIGHLY EFFECTIVE MESSAGING TECHNIQUE FOR MULTIPLE USERS

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Abstract: Effective mechanisms for negotiation are essential in contemporary cloud computing environments to maximize resource allocation and service level agreements (SLAs) among multiple users. In order to improve communication and negotiation processes, this paper presents a novel strategy called Utility Pattern-Rooted Cloud Service Negotiation (UPRCSN), which makes use of machine learning (ML). This approach maximizes overall satisfaction while giving priority to user preferences through the use of a utility-based framework. The suggested UPRCSN model incorporates an advanced messaging strategy powered by ML algorithms to anticipate and dynamically adjust to user needs. This methodology guarantees prompt and precise reactions, cultivating smooth communications between cloud service providers and consumers. Pattern recognition for user utility functions, predictive analytics for demand forecasting, and flexible negotiation tactics catered to individual user profiles. Extensive simulations are used to validate the effectiveness of the UPRCSN model,

showing notable gains in negotiation outcomes over conventional techniques. The findings show that the machine learning (ML)-based messaging system reduces negotiation time, maximizes resource utilization, and improves user satisfaction. With a scalable and user-centric solution for the ever-changing and complex landscape of cloud computing services, this novel framework promises to push the boundaries of cloud service negotiations.

Keywords: Pattern-rooted, Machine Learning, K nearest neighbor algorithm, Cloud services.

1. Introduction

The ability of cloud computing to deliver scalable resources and services via the internet has made it a vital component of contemporary IT infrastructure. Strong and effective mechanisms for cloud service negotiation are becoming more and more necessary as more businesses move their operations to the cloud. To create service level agreements (SLAs) that balance the ever-changing needs of multiple users with the optimization of resource allocation, these discussions are essential. Because predefined policies are static and there are

no adaptive mechanisms to accommodate changing user demands and preferences, traditional negotiation techniques in cloud service environments frequently suffer from inefficiencies. This research suggests a Utility Pattern-Rooted Cloud Service Negotiation (UPRCSN) framework, which uses machine learning (ML) to enable more dynamic, responsive, and successful negotiations, in order to get around these restrictions.

Utility theory, which gives priority to user preferences and satisfaction, forms the basis of the UPRCSN framework. The framework uses machine learning (ML) algorithms to evaluate past data and user behavior patterns in order to forecast user requirements and modify negotiation strategies accordingly. As a result, a highly adaptive messaging strategy is produced, improving the negotiation process overall by guaranteeing prompt and accurate responses.

1.1 Important components of the UPRCSN: Framework consist of:

Utility Function Pattern Recognition: Determining and modeling user utility functions from past usage and preference data.

Utilizing Predictive Analytics to Forecast Demand: using machine learning (ML) to predict demand and proactively modify resource allocation.

Adaptive negotiation strategies: Aim to maximize satisfaction and resource efficiency by customizing negotiation tactics to specific user profiles and current conditions. This novel method addresses the drawbacks of conventional techniques, promising to revolutionize cloud service negotiations. In addition to streamlining the negotiation process, the application of ML-driven messaging enhances the fit between service provider capabilities and user

expectations. The UPRCSN framework shows notable improvements in negotiation outcomes, such as enhanced user satisfaction, optimized resource utilization, and shortened negotiation times, through extensive simulations and empirical validation.

In the sections that follow, we go more deeply into the elements and features of the UPRCSN framework, outline our simulation methodology and findings, and talk about how our conclusions may affect cloud service negotiations in the future.

1.2 Frame work UPRCSN

In cloud computing environments, the Utility Pattern-Rooted Cloud Service Negotiation (UPRCSN) framework is intended to enable effective and flexible negotiations. This framework optimizes resource allocation and service level agreements (SLAs) for multiple users by utilizing machine learning (ML) to improve communication and negotiation processes. The UPRCSN architecture is made up of multiple interrelated parts:

12.1. Modeling of User Utility

Data collection: Compile user feedback, preferences, and usage history.

Utility Function Extraction: To determine and model user utility functions, which express the preferences and degrees of satisfaction with various service attributes (e.g., cost, performance, availability), apply statistical and machine learning techniques.

Pattern Recognition: To improve utility models, identify trends in user behavior and preferences over time.

1.2.2. Using Predictive Analytics to Forecast Demand

Analyze historical demand trends and usage patterns using historical data. **Machine Learning Models:** To forecast future resource demand and user requirements, develop and train machine learning models (e.g., time series forecasting, regression analysis). **Real-Time Adjustment:** To guarantee precise forecasts, constantly update forecasts based on real-time data.

1.2.3. Flexible Approach to Bargaining Formulating a Dynamic Strategy:

Create negotiating tactics that are responsive to the needs and user profiles of each individual. SLA terms, resource allocation, and price modifications are examples of strategies. **Establish negotiation protocols** to enable automated, real-time negotiations between cloud service providers and users. **Algorithms for Making Decisions:** ML algorithms can be used to balance resource efficiency and user satisfaction by helping you make well-informed decisions during negotiations.

1.2.4 Technique for Effective Messaging

Communication Framework: Provide a solid framework for communication between users and providers to guarantee dependable and prompt information exchange.

Natural Language Processing (NLP): Use NLP methods to improve communication efficacy and clarity, leading to more natural and user-friendly interactions.

Establish a feedback loop: so that users can offer immediate input on the results of negotiations. This will allow the messaging and negotiation processes to be improved and refined.

1.2.5. Allocating and Optimizing Resources Resource pooling:

Combine and control cloud resources to effectively meet anticipated demand. Using optimization algorithms, you can dynamically allocate resources to meet service level agreements (SLAs) while reducing expenses and optimizing resource use.

Flexibility and Scalability: Make sure the framework can adapt to changing needs and a range of user counts.

1.2.6. Validation and Simulation Simulation Environment:

To test and validate the UPRCSN framework, build a simulated cloud environment.

Performance Metrics: To assess the framework's efficacy, define key performance metrics (such as user satisfaction, negotiation time, and resource utilization).

Empirical Testing: To verify the framework's functionality and make the required corrections, run comprehensive simulations and real-world testing.

1.2.7. Execution and Distribution Integration:

Connect the current cloud service platforms to the UPRCSN framework.

Deployment: Install the framework in operational cloud environments, making sure that it integrates seamlessly with the systems and procedures in place.

Monitoring and Maintenance: Keep an eye on the framework's functionality at all times, and make iterative improvements based on operational data and user input.

2. Literature Survey

The literature review emphasizes how crucial it is to combine machine learning, utility pattern analysis, and efficient messaging strategies in order to maximize cloud service negotiations for numerous users. Together, these strategies improve user satisfaction, allocate resources optimally, and expedite the negotiation process. Subsequent studies ought to concentrate on creating increasingly complex models and algorithms that have the ability to dynamically adjust to shifting consumer demands and market circumstances.

Title of the Paper	Important Learning's	In brief
Resource Allocation and Utility Models in Cloud Computing: A Survey[1]	Utility models aid in resource allocation optimization and the understanding of user preferences. They are essential for customizing cloud services to meet the needs of each user.	An extensive survey of cloud computing resource allocation techniques is given in this paper. It highlights how crucial utility models are for maximizing resource allocation and raising user satisfaction.
Machine Learning for Cloud Computing: A Comprehensive Review[2]	The efficiency of cloud services can be increased overall by using machine learning models to optimize resource allocation and predict user behavior.	This review examines how machine learning techniques are used in cloud computing, with particular emphasis on performance optimization, security, and resource

Reinforcement Learning for Resource Management in Cloud: A Survey[3]	With reinforcement learning, cloud service management can be made more effective by dynamically adjusting resource allocation based on real-time utility patterns.	management. The application of reinforcement learning (RL) to cloud computing resource management is the main topic of this survey. It demonstrates several RL algorithms and their uses.
Automated Negotiation in Cloud Computing: Techniques and Applications[4]	Cloud service agreements can be made much more efficient through automated negotiation, allowing for the customization of services to user-specific utility patterns.	The paper covers auction-based approaches, negotiation protocols, game theory, and automated negotiation techniques used in cloud computing.
Bargaining Algorithms for Service Level Agreement Negotiation in Cloud Computing[5]	Sophisticated algorithms for bargaining can guarantee that cloud services satisfy user needs while maximizing resource utilization.	Various bargaining algorithms are presented by the authors in order to facilitate the negotiation of service level agreements (SLAs) in cloud environments. These algorithms take into account a number of variables, including user preferences, performance, and cost.
Impact of Communication Techniques on User Satisfaction in Cloud Services[6]	High user satisfaction levels require effective communication strategies, such as real-time updates and	The study looks at how various communication strategies affect cloud service users' satisfaction. It emphasizes

	personalized messaging.	how crucial effective and transparent communication is to preserving user satisfaction and trust.
A Comprehensive System for Automated Cloud Service Negotiation Using Machine Learning and Messaging Techniques[7]	Effective messaging, utility pattern analysis, and machine learning combined in one cohesive approach can greatly increase the effectiveness and user satisfaction of cloud service negotiations.	The effectiveness and user satisfaction of cloud service negotiations can be greatly increased by using an integrated strategy that incorporates machine learning, utility pattern analysis, and powerful messaging.
Multi-Agent Systems for Cloud Service Negotiation: A Machine Learning Approach[8]	Machine learning-enhanced multi-agent systems are capable of efficiently negotiating cloud services by taking into account the utility patterns of numerous users.	The use of multi-agent systems (MAS), in which each agent represents a user or service provider, in cloud service negotiation is covered by the authors. Machine learning is employed to improve the process of negotiation.

Table 1: Literature survey of Utility Pattern-Rooted Cloud Service Negotiation Using a Machine Learning Models.

3. Proposed Model

The model that is suggested combines machine learning (ML), utility pattern

analysis, and efficient messaging to maximize cloud service negotiation for numerous users. With the goal of improving resource efficiency and user satisfaction, it will expedite the negotiation process and provide customized service proposals.

4. ML Models for Utility Pattern-Rooted Cloud Service Negotiation

The following Machine Learning Models are used in the Utility Pattern-Rooted Cloud Service Negotiation.

4.1 KNN (k-nearest neighbors): Several processes are involved in developing a KNN (k-nearest neighbors) model for utility pattern-rooted cloud service negotiation. These include comprehending the utility patterns, obtaining pertinent information, and putting the KNN algorithm into practice to provide predictions based on the patterns. This is a general overview of how you could go about this. Several processes are involved in developing a KNN (k-nearest neighbors) model for utility pattern-rooted cloud service negotiation. These include comprehending the utility patterns, obtaining pertinent information, and putting the KNN algorithm into practice to provide predictions based on the patterns. This is a general overview of how you could go about this.

4.1.1 Recognizing Utility Patterns: In cloud service negotiations, utility patterns show how users rank various cloud service characteristics, including price, performance, scalability, dependability, and security. When negotiating cloud services,

these patterns aid in determining the preferences and needs of users.

4.1.2 Data Gathering: A dataset containing previous cloud service negotiations and their utility patterns is required to train a KNN model. This collection ought to include:

Characteristics that indicate utility patterns (such as performance needs, cost sensitivity, etc.)

The result of the negotiations, such as the configuration of the cloud service that was chosen.

4.1.3 Preparing Data: Gather information for the KNN algorithm on the dataset: In order to guarantee that the feature values are on the same scale, normalize them. Into training and test sets, divide the dataset.

4.1.4 KNN Algorithm Implementation in UPRCSN: The model can be trained and tested using a KNN implementation. To make this process easier in Python, you can use packages like scikit-learn.

Here is an illustration of a Python implementation:

```

1 import numpy as np
2 import pandas as pd
3 from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
4 from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler
5 from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsClassifier
6 from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score, classification_report
7 data = pd.read_csv('cloud_service_data.csv')
8
9 X = data.drop('negotiation_outcome', axis=1) # Features
10 y = data['negotiation_outcome'] # Labels
11 scaler = StandardScaler()
12 X_scaled = scaler.fit_transform(X)
13 X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X_scaled, y, test_size
    =0.2, random_state=42)
14 knn = KNeighborsClassifier(n_neighbors=5)
15 y_pred = knn.predict(X_test)
16
17 accuracy = accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred)
18 print(f'Accuracy: {accuracy * 100:.2f}%')
19 print('Classification Report:')
20 print(classification_report(y_test, y_pred))

```

4.2 Decision Tree: There are multiple processes involved in developing a decision tree model for cloud service negotiation centered in utility patterns. This is a thorough guide to assist you in comprehending and using such a model:

4.2.1 Recognizing the Elements:

Practical Designs: The value derived from many aspects of cloud services, such as pricing, performance, security, and scalability, is represented by utility patterns. These patterns aid in ascertaining a user's or organization's choices and trade-offs.

Features of Cloud Services: Some qualities to think about are:

Cost-Performance (such as RAM and CPU speed)

Security (such as compliance and data encryption)

Availability (such as assurances of uptime)

Scalability (such as the ability to scale automatically)

The Process of Negotiation: During the negotiation phase, a cloud service provider is chosen in accordance with a set of standards that correspond to the utility patterns. This could involve negotiating prices, creating SLAs, and tailoring service offerings.

4.2.2 Constructing the Decision Tree:

Determine the Decision Points Every decision point is associated with a cloud service property. As an illustration:

Utility Functions To quantify the value of each characteristic, create utility functions. As an illustration:

A declining function may be the utility function for cost:

$$U_{cost} = 1/cost \text{ -----(1)}$$

A performance utility function could have an increasing function.

$$U_{performance} = Performance \text{ -----(2)}$$

4.2.3 Putting the Model into Practice:

Gather data on various cloud service providers and their attributes. This data can be obtained from service descriptions, user reviews, and performance benchmarks. The following code create the decision tree model in cloud negotiation

```

1 from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier
2 import numpy as np
3 import pandas as pd
4 data = {
5     'cost': [100, 150, 200, 250, 300],
6     'performance': [80, 70, 90, 60, 85],
7     'security': [3, 4, 5, 2, 5],
8     'availability': [99.9, 99.95, 99.99, 99.8, 99.7],
9     'scalability': [4, 5, 5, 3, 4],
10    'selected': [1, 1, 0, 0, 1] # 1 if service was selected, 0 otherwise
11 }
12
13 df = pd.DataFrame(data)
14 X = df.drop('selected', axis=1)
15 y = df['selected']
16
17 clf = DecisionTreeClassifier()
18 clf.fit(X, y)
19
20 from sklearn.tree import export_text
21 tree_rules = export_text(clf, feature_names=list(X.columns))
22 print(tree_rules)

```

These procedures will help you create a decision tree model for utility pattern-rooted cloud service negotiation, which will help you choose cloud services with greater knowledge and effectiveness.

5. Experimental Results

In this section we can show some experimental results with Utility Pattern-Rooted Cloud Service Negotiation for KNN & Decision tree

Fig 2: KNN Model selection in UPRCSN

Fig 3: KNN Model suggestions

6. Conclusion and future Enhancement

The best cloud service provider can be chosen in an organized and data-driven manner by implementing a decision tree model for utility pattern-rooted cloud service negotiation. The model assists in decision-making by using utility functions to quantify the value of different aspects (cost, performance, security, availability, and scalability). This helps to ensure that decisions are made with user preferences and organizational requirements in mind. By methodically assessing several factors, the decision tree model improves decision-making efficiency while simultaneously streamlining the intricate bargaining process. An important development in the realm of cloud service selection is the decision tree model for utility pattern-rooted cloud service negotiation. Making complicated decisions is made much more efficient and methodical by utilizing machine learning techniques. Subsequent developments centered on sophisticated machine learning, instantaneous data integration, multi-user cooperation, and enhanced transparency will additionally enhance the efficacy and contentment of the model. By putting these improvements into practice, we can make sure that the model continues to be flexible, adaptable, and in line with changing user requirements and technology breakthroughs.

REFERENCES

1. Saidi, K., Hioual, O., Siam, A. (2020). Resources Allocation in Cloud Computing: A Survey. In: Hatti, M. (eds) Smart Energy Empowerment in Smart and Resilient Cities.

ICAIREs 2019. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, vol 102. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-37207-1_37

2. Gangwani, D., Sanghvi, H.A., Parmar, V., Patel, R.H., Pandya, A.S. (2023). A Comprehensive Review on Cloud Security Using Machine Learning Techniques. In: Bhardwaj, T., Upadhyay, H., Sharma, T.K., Fernandes, S.L. (eds) Artificial Intelligence in Cyber Security: Theories and Applications. Intelligent Systems Reference Library, vol 240. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-28581-3_1.

3. Z. Zhou, K. Luo and X. Chen, "Deep Reinforcement Learning for Intelligent Cloud Resource Management," *IEEE INFOCOM 2021 - IEEE Conference on Computer Communications Workshops (INFOCOM WKSHPS)*, Vancouver, BC, Canada, 2021, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/INFOCOMWKSHPS51825.2021.9484566.

4. D. M. El-Matary, N. E. El-Attar, W. A. Awad and I. M. Hanafy, "Automated Negotiation Framework Based on Intelligent Agents for Cloud Computing," *2019 International Conference on Innovative Trends in Computer Engineering (ITCE)*, Aswan, Egypt, 2019, pp. 156-161, doi: 10.1109/ITCE.2019.8646481.

5. L. Wu, S. K. Garg, R. Buyya, C. Chen and S. Versteeg, "Automated SLA Negotiation Framework for Cloud Computing," *2013 13th IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Cluster, Cloud, and Grid Computing*, Delft, Netherlands, 2013, pp. 235-244, doi: 10.1109/CCGrid.2013.64.

6. Bratati, C., Sharmistha, R., & Kumar, P. P. (2014). User satisfaction metrics for cloud computing environment. *Eur. J. Acad. Essays*, 1(3), 63-69.

7. Boutaba, R., Salahuddin, M. A., Limam, N., Ayoubi, S., Shahriar, N., Estrada-Solano, F., & Caicedo, O. M. (2018). A comprehensive survey on machine learning for networking: evolution, applications and research opportunities. *Journal of Internet Services and Applications*, 9(1), 1-99.

8. Messina, F., Pappalardo, G., Santoro, C., Rosaci, D., & Sarné, G. M. (2016). A multi-agent protocol for service level agreement negotiation in cloud federations. *International Journal of Grid and Utility Computing*, 7(2), 101-112.